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Micromechanics of Hydraulic Fracturing and Damage in Rock Based on DEM Modeling

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study of the micromechanics of the coupled hydro-mechanical (H-M) behavior of brittle rock during hydraulic fracturing. The study is conducted using the Discrete Element Method (DEM), which spatially discretizes a rock mass into discrete disc particles, coupled with a solver for modeling fluid flow through a network of connected pores. In the coupled H-M DEM modeling, fluid flows through newly formed hydraulic fractures due to pore pressure increase from fluid injection in a wellbore and is coupled with rock mechanical response across a wide range of flow rates. The micromechanical insights from the DEM modeling provide better understanding of coupled H-M processes which precede rock breakdown during hydraulic fracturing, and the transition in deformation in brittle rock from a single hydraulic fracture to branched hydraulic fractures and a diffused damage zone. The effects of the properties of the fracturing fluid and the rock matrix as well as the effects of loading flow rate on the development of pressure-induced deformation and fracturing in crystalline brittle rocks fracturing are investigated. The DEM models used properties that were obtained by calibrating flow-rate-dependent stress-strain response against previously published experimental data on brittle rocks (granite in particular). DEM results are compared with experimental results from a true-triaxial scale model testing on hydraulic fracturing in an analogue rock. The presented results are expected to enable better understanding of conditions

which lead to successful fracture propagation versus damage and fracture arrest in geo-reservoirs.

Keywords: Hydro-mechanical modeling, Geo-reservoirs, Discrete Element Method, Hydraulic fracturing, Rock mass, Rock permeability enhancement.

1. Introduction

This paper investigates the mechanisms which lead to fracture propagation and/or damage in brittle rock mass during hydraulic fracturing processes. Hydraulic fracturing is a technique for permeability enhancement of rock masses in deep geo-reservoirs, which is achieved by propagating new fractures via pressurized fluid from a wellbore previously drilled into the reservoir [1, 2]. In Enhanced Geothermal Systems (EGS), the reservoir rock is typically crystalline and has permeability lower than 10^{-3} μD [3], and hydraulic fracturing is often employed to create a permeable path to circulate fluid and heat from an injection point to a producing well.

Most hydraulic fracturing models used in practice assume that the local tangential stresses in a homogeneous, triaxially compressed rock around the wellbore are increasing due to borehole pressurization until the rock mass breaks down in tension. Hydraulic fracturing models used in practice still assume that the rock stress-strain relationships follow linear elasticity, and fracture propagation follows linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM). Hydraulic fracturing simulators are based on simplified, often two-dimensional prediction of fracture shape and usually offer only smooth fracture surface propagation, without taking into account local heterogeneities and damage in rock [4]. Early developments of hydraulic fracturing modeling included two-dimensional and three-dimensional versions assuming linear elasticity [2, 4–8]. Two recent developments in hydraulic fracturing simulators focus on bridging multi-scale problems and the interactions between natural existing fractures and hydraulic induced fractures, and include: 1) the Discrete Fracture Network (DFN) model with stress shadowing of existing fracture, and 2) Unconventional Fracture Model (UFM) [9–12]. Other methods for modeling hydraulic fracturing at micro-scale include: 1) implicit mechanical technique using Voronoi grains coupled with explicit fluid flow solution through channels using parallel-plate cubic law [13], 2) Numerical Manifold Method for three-dimensional remeshing-free fracture propagation in rock [14, 15], 3) peridynamics theories [16–21], 4) theoretical models based on experimental rock testing [22], 5) Johnson-Holmquist rock (JHR) model in the commercial software LS-DYNA [23], 6) diffusive phase-field method (PFM) [24–26], 7)

mesh-free smooth particle hydrodynamics (SPH) [27], 8) equivalent continuum-dual porosity model [28], 9) displacement correlation method within the hybrid Finite Element-Meshfree Method (FEMM) [29], and 10) extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) [30–37] and most recently Discrete Element Methods [38–41]. Different cohesive zone models within the framework of LEFM assume a small cohesive zone compared to the fracture length [42]. To conclude, all the existing hydraulic fracturing models still rely on LEFM solutions.

In practical applications of hydraulic fracturing, the measured net fracturing pressures are usually higher than those predicted by models [43]. It has been argued that higher net pressures are due to several factors, including better than expected containment, poor measurement of closure stress, near-wellbore effects, complex fracturing, poor understanding of rheology, and rock heterogeneity and nonlinearity. Crack tip effects can lead to scale effect on fracture toughness for field-size fractures. The un-wetted zone in front of the crack tip has a lower pressure than the closure pressure and can clamp the fracture tip to locally reduce the stress intensity in the rock. From shallow-depth hydraulic fracturing experiment, sizable fluid leg zones were found [44]. In conclusion, the possibility of large damage zone and plasticity around the fracture tip may invalidate LEFM. Hydraulic fracture propagation velocity depends on fluid and rock properties. Although lot of work has been done on fracture propagation in rocks due to different loading, hydraulic fracture propagation has not yet been fully understood particularly from the micromechanical perspective. Hydraulic fracturing mechanisms, which produce, need to be evaluated.

The aim of this paper is to address knowledge gaps related to the conditions which lead to rock mass response from an ideal single tensile hydraulic fracture to branched fractures and a damaged zone due to fluid injection. Micromechanical understanding is improved through the Discrete Element Method (DEM) by investigating the detailed growth of a hydraulic fracture from the wellbore. DEM spatially discretizes the rock mass into discrete particles that interact at their contacts and can explicitly model fracture propagation and micro-crack type damage at the grain scale. In this study, the DEM mechanical model is coupled with a solver for porous media fluid flow to model the coupled hydro-mechanical (H-M) processes responsible for hydraulic fracturing. Coupled H-M DEM models fluid flow through the newly formed hydraulic fractures and pore pressure increase in permeable rock matrix due to pressurization in a wellbore. The stress-strain response of the DEM model is calibrated against previously published experimental data on rocks under different loading and flow rates. Loading rate in the model corresponds to the flow rate of fracturing fluid injected in the fluid flow reservoir at the model borehole. Strain rate is a calculated rate of radial strain (in polar

coordinates) to which the borehole wall has been subjected to due to the pressurization over time. Strain rate from radial pressurization of the borehole wall is calculated using the respective flow rate and average elastic modulus of synthetic rock. Hydraulic fracturing induces impact loading by increasing the volume of fluid injected into the borehole in each time step which will correspond to the calculated impact strain rate. Stress waves propagate through the DEM assembly via contacts between particles from one particle to another, therefore the model response is a consequence of the explicit wave propagation. The dynamic stress term refers to the change of stress across different flow rates. Better understanding of conditions which lead to either single clean fracture propagation or hydraulic fracturing energy dissipation through fracture tip processes, damage and fracture branching will help engineers, industry and society to better utilize underground resources through advancing hydraulic-fracturing-predictive models and technologies.

2. Coupled Hydro-Mechanical Discrete Element Method

The Discrete Element Method (DEM) has been widely used for numerical modeling of particulate interactions for over three decades [45]. DEM uses an explicit finite difference method for solving the trajectories and velocities of individual discrete particles which interact at their contacts in a particulate system over time. At each time step, the motion of particles is calculated due to forces that are applied to each particle following Newton's second law of motion. Forces which are applied to particle centers come from boundary loads and interactions with neighboring particles at particle contacts, walls, volume forces and fluid. Particle-to-particle interactions are modeled via spring and damper elements parallel and normal to the particle contacts.

The Bonded Particle Model (BPM), formulated and validated to account for bonding between particles in rocks, is used in this study [45, 46]. The BPM is integrated within the two-dimensional Particle Flow Code (PFC2D) [47]. BPM enhances the DEM capability from modeling granular assemblies towards modeling geomaterials with cohesion. In BPM, particles are bonded together with parallel bonds which can be pictured as cementation at the particle contacts for transferring forces and bending moments and area assigned with normal and shear stiffness. As a result, a solid comprised of bonded particles can be assembled and damaged. In addition, the main advantage of BPM is that fracturing across scales varying from the individual bond size to the model size can be directly observed and analyzed. Although the particles are rigid, the contact stiffnesses between are calibrated by adjusting spring normal and shear stiffnesses giving the granular assembly elasticity. The bond breakage between

particles can occur at any time during the simulation at multiple locations and is driven when local contact forces exceed the bond strength. In the process, fracturing can be simulated.

Hydro-mechanical coupling is modeled at the individual particle scale which is the smallest spatial discretization unit of the model. A network of fluid flow channels is formed at each particle contact, and the fluid flow channels are linked together through fluid reservoirs located spatially between particles to ensure the mass conservation and the transient fluid flow solution. Fig. 1 illustrates the network of fluid channels and reservoirs. Fluid flow in channels in 2D will produce similar effect as fluid flow in pipes into 3D rock matrix for the case where rock permeability is isotropic. The channels are initially considered dry, since the emphasis of this work is on hydraulic fracturing of porous and permeable dry crystalline rock. Numerically, the fluid flow through a network of fluid channels and reservoirs is solved with finite differences and is superimposed on the DEM particulate model. DEM particles discretize the solid stress-strain field while fluid flow is modeled for channels and fractures through synthetic rock. The fluid flow rate Q in a fluid channel between two particles is calculated using the parallel plate flow solution of Navier-Stokes equation for incompressible Newtonian fluid and laminar flow [48]:

$$Q = \frac{d^3 \Delta P}{12 \mu L} \quad (1)$$

where d = fluid channel aperture; ΔP = pressure difference of the reservoirs at two ends of the channel; μ = dynamic fluid viscosity; and L = fluid channel length. The length of the fluid channel section between two particles is equal to the average diameter of two contacting particles. It is assumed that each contact has residual initial fluid channel aperture d_0 when the normal contact force is at its prescribed residual value, which is useful for modeling permeable rock. The increase in normal load decreases the apparent fluid channel aperture in the case of compressive normal contact force:

$$d = \frac{d_0 F_0}{\Delta F + F_0} \quad (2)$$

where ΔF = the normal contact force increment, and $F_0 = F$'s residual value at d_0 . For the case of tensile normal contact force:

$$d = d_0 + ma \quad (3)$$

where m = arbitrary chosen dimensionless multiplier which can be set different from unity for calibration purposes and a = physical distance between two particle contacts adjacent to the fluid flow channel at the beginning of each time step. Therefore, the fluid channel aperture is subjected to change and compliant to the local strain change in the rock model, which enables transient and spatial variations in rock matrix permeability and fracture aperture. Furthermore, the fluid channel aperture corresponds to the actual distance between particle surfaces at each time-step. However, it is also possible to modify the equation that determines the local fluid channel width (Eqs. 2 and 3), for example for keeping the width of the channel constant during cycling, or to model effects of dissolution/precipitation of rock minerals. Eq. (2) describes the calculation of the fluid channel aperture as a function of initial value and the normal compressive contact force between particles when the compressive force increase has a positive sign and particles are overlapping. Therefore, the fluid channel aperture decreases if the normal contact force is compressive or $\Delta F > 0$. If the normal contact force is flagged as tensile, or $\Delta F < 0$, Eq. (3) is used instead. If $\Delta F = 0$, the fluid channel aperture remains the same as in the previous time step.

The increase in fluid pressure in a fluid reservoir due to the change volume of fluids in the reservoirs and fluid flow is calculated as:

$$\Delta P = \frac{K_f}{V_d} (\Sigma q \Delta t - \Delta V_d) \quad (4)$$

where K_f = fluid bulk modulus;, V_d = volume of the fluid; ΔV_d = change in volume of the fluid due to mechanical, pressure, temperature changes; q = fluid flow rate; and Δt = time step. Finally, it is assumed that the fluid flow through a fluid channel is localized at the corresponding contact, and the pressure region of the fluid reservoir is uniform, leading to the tractions that are independent of the path around the fluid reservoir. For the polygonal path that joins the contacts which surround the fluid reservoir, the force vector F_i on a particle is:

$$F_i = P n_i s \quad (5)$$

were n_i = the unit normal vector of the line joining the two contact points on the particle and s = the length of the line.

To recapitulate, the DEM-BPM model is coupled with fluid flow through the rock matrix and rock fractures. The local rock permeability is compliant with the local stress-strain changes in the rock, which can be caused by loading, fracture propagation, development of microcracks,

or a change in boundary conditions. An important and unique feature of DEM-BPM is enabling of fracture propagation in a self-oriented manner, completely independent of previously prescribed parameters such as are the fracture width, length or height. Although the intermediate principal boundary stress affects rock strength, many hydraulic fracturing studies of planar fractures have been performed in 2D. This study investigates the transition between quasi-static and directly and indirectly induced dynamic rock fracturing, where the latter exhibits damage in all directions and is independent of the in-situ confining stress direction. Although shear cracks are important for rock failure, this paper studies quasi-brittle hydraulic fracture propagation in isotropic permeable rock, which advances with least resistance in tensile mode according to LEFM. Then, the effects of increasing flow rates and changes in fluid viscosity pumped in the borehole are investigated and compared to the quasi-static fracturing. The transient nature of the coupled DEM and fluid flow modeling enables studying of rock behavior from micromechanical perspective. It provides better understanding of the conditions under which damage laden by excessive microcracks occurs and how it affects the main tensile fracture propagation and hydraulic fracture properties.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. DEM Model Setup and Parameter Calibration

To investigate the coupled H-M microscale aspects of hydraulic fracturing of geo-reservoirs in brittle rocks, the two-dimensional DEM model of hydraulic fracture initiation and propagation is built. Particle size, or spatial model discretization, are chosen to be small enough to ensure stability of the model and general fracture propagation orientation, and sufficiently large to enable reasonable modeling time. Particles are modeled as disks; average number of particles is several thousand in models. The effect of particle size and distribution was not investigated further specifically because the model is not geared towards understanding of rock heterogeneities. The models are biaxially compressed with far-field in situ horizontal stresses and pressurized at the borehole with injection flow rates between 10.0 and 33.0 l/s (liters per second).

Table 1 lists the model initial and boundary conditions used. Semi-rigid wall elements with normal stiffness of $k_n=200$ GPa, shear stiffness of $k_s=77$ GPa, and friction coefficient of 0.0 are placed on the model boundaries to confine the sample. Boundary stresses were applied on the stiff boundaries through a servo-wall mechanism where the normal velocities of the wall

elements are constantly adjusted during the time-stepping procedure to maintain the prescribed boundary stress. Table 1 was added to summarize the boundary stresses and wall element data.

Tables 2 and 3 show the macro- and micro-mechanical parameters obtained from simulated direct tension and notched-beam tests in PFC^{2D} which are compared with average values from the literature [45, 46, 49]. The procedures for obtaining granite-like macro-properties and for testing the micro-mechanical properties for DEM-BPM followed recommendations from Potyondy and Cundall (2004). It is important to mention that the listed micro- and macro- mechanical parameters are obtained for this model with the chosen size of DEM particles. DEM particles do not represent physical grains of the rock, but they are means of spatial model discretization in DEM. The effects of spatial variability of mechanical and hydraulic rock properties is not considered in this study. The synthetic rock uses various particles sizes for creating dense particle assembly in DEM, but the mechanical and hydraulic properties of such assembly are homogeneous even at a small scale. If different DEM particle size is chosen, the parameter matching procedure needs to be repeated for the different particle size. Simulation of permeability tests in PFC^{2D} uses the constant flow technique, which is suitable for testing low-permeability geo-materials [50, 51].

The Darcy fluid flow equation is used for determining the initial value of the average permeability of the tested rock sample with the prescribed initial width of fluid channels. During cycling for the permeability testing, the bond-breakage is disabled by setting the bond strengths unrealistically high. The no-bond-breakage model enables the use of high flow rates and low fluid dynamic viscosities, which aids in saving computational time in the permeability matching. The tested rock sample has dimensions 5 x 5 cm² (Fig. 2a). Viscous fluid flows into the specimen at a constant flow rate on the left boundary, and the pressure differences across the model are recorded at prescribed times during the test. The final pressure difference is recorded following the test convergence, as shown in Fig. 2b. By numerically simulating the recommended procedures for laboratory testing of low permeability geo-materials, the recorded pressure was used together with the flow rate in Darcy's equation for calculating permeability. The numerical relationship between the initial average synthetic-rock permeability and the model parameters of the initial fluid flow channel are established and shown in Fig. 3. Target values of the experimental granite permeability [52] can be obtained in the model by adjusting the initial fluid channel aperture using Fig. 3a.

3.2. Validation of the DEM Model

For qualitative validation of the micromechanical models, the experimental results from laboratory scale-model simulations of hydraulic fracturing in a block sample of granite are used [57, 58]. The cited references provide complete technical details of the in-house built custom large scale true triaxial cell, systems for applying, controlling and monitoring far field stresses and borehole fluid flow and pressures to the rock sample. Granite block samples are 30 x 30 x 30 cm³ in size, with a vertical borehole drilled from the top of the sample cased with a tubing. Hydraulic fracturing was performed under quasi-static flow rates by slow pumping of water and motor oil into the borehole and initiated from the uncased bottom section of the borehole. Results from two tests are used in the validation: 1) an unloaded/unconfined block sample hydraulically fractured with water ($\mu=0.001$ Pa·s), and 2) a true-triaxially loaded block sample with different magnitudes of principal stresses ($\sigma_1=13$ MPa, $\sigma_2=\sigma_3=8$ MPa) hydraulically fractured with high viscosity oil ($\mu=0.072$ Pa·s). In test 1), the fracture pressure is theoretically equal to the tensile strength σ_t of the rock, while in test 2) the fracture pressure is theoretically equal to the sum of the tensile strength and the minimum principal stress $\sigma_t + \sigma_3$. Two fluids of different viscosities are used to give insight into the effect of fluid infiltration to the rock matrix on the fracture shape and breakdown pressure on confined and unconfined granite block.

In the experiments, fracture was branching in the borehole vicinity, but the general fracture plane occurred in the direction perpendicular to the minimum confining stress. Fig. 4 shows results of experiment using water ($\mu=0.001$ Pa·s) as hydraulic fracturing fluid. Water is colored blue to investigate flow in the rock matrix and identify new fractures. A thin fracture initiates from the wellbore, but the water also infiltrates rock as a cloud around the wellbore. Fig. 5 shows evolution of microcracks in laboratory experiment, which occur around the wellbore when using the high viscosity fluid, and in all three cases the propagating fracture does not exist. Additional evidence from Acoustic Emission (AE) measurement supported the conclusions, where high viscosity fluid test produced more AE events than the test with low viscosity fracturing fluid [59]. Similar damage zones, which are oval shaped around the wellbore with a longer axis in the direction perpendicular to the minimum confining far-field stress, occur in synthetic rock as it will be seen in the results. Although a distinction between tensile and shear microcracks is not visible, a distinguishable damaged zone, which is a dark grey-colored area indicates increased cracking and fluid infiltration in experiments, as shown in Fig 5a. The comparison in Figs. 5a and b shows a good qualitative agreement between the

modeling and experiment, which illustrates the validity of the DEM modeling. Additionally, Fig. 5b shows that tensile microcracks are dominating the damage area around the wellbore.

3.3. Effect of Pressurized Fluid Flow Rate on Hydraulic Fracturing

Fracturing and failure in quasi-brittle materials under strain-controlled loading depends on the applied rate of the pressurization. Previous research shows that the fracture initiation stress for a penny-shaped fracture in rock increases significantly with the increasing loading rates [53]. The fracture initiation stress is the external stress applied to the specimen, which is used to calculate the stress intensity factor at the crack tip. The high measured tensile strength during high loading rates has been explained because of many fractures starting at the same time under impact loading. First, the DEM model is tested to see if the method is suitable for modeling material response across a wide range of loading flow rates from very low quasi-static of 10^{-6} s^{-1} to a “fast” loading of $100 s^{-1}$.

The fracture initiation stress that leads to crack activation σ_c depends on the cube root of the strain rate for a penny-shaped initial crack [53]:

$$\sigma_c = 3 \sqrt[3]{\frac{9\pi EK_{IC}^2}{16N^2 C_2}} \sqrt[3]{\frac{d\varepsilon_0}{dt}} \quad (6)$$

where σ_c is the fracture stress, $d\varepsilon_0/dt$ is the constant strain rate, E is the Young’s modulus, K_{IC} is the fracture toughness, N is the coefficient for a penny-shaped crack ($N=1.12$) and c_2 is the p -wave velocity for rock. **The fracture initiation stress σ_c is the sum of external minimum principal stress applied to the specimen and the tensile strength of the rock mass at the point of initial fracture propagation.** At high constant strain rates σ_c is a strong function of the strain rate for a given crack size, and σ_c becomes independent of the crack geometry [53]. Rock fractures form along multiple micro-cracks at the same time, where fracturing can be characterized with bifurcation and branching.

Kirsch’s solution for maximum tensile stress can be used as a guide for fracture initiation criterion at a location where the maximum hoop stress increases the tensile strength of the rock at the wellbore wall [54]. The DEM model behavior is compared to the theoretical solution in Eq. (6) for dynamic loading and against the Kirsch’s solution at quasi-static flow rates. Table 4 shows the obtained results, which are plotted in the Fig. 6. As shown, DEM can replicate brittle rock behavior across a wide span of flow rates. The predicted rate-dependent fracture resistance is attributed to the dynamic formulation used in PFC, where the stress propagates following the wave equation. Due to stress wave propagation, higher flow rates lead to higher

stress concentration at the crack tip before enough bonds are broken to cause fracture propagation or damage. As a result, fracture resistance increases with increasing flow rate. This rate-dependent response is shown and further discussed micro-mechanically below. However, DEM approach is affected by the particle size or spatial discretization, because the fracture path is dictated by the orientations and positions of the DEM particle contacts, which are envisioned as micro-cracks or fracture segments upon breaking. A step further from the DEM-BP model towards studying characteristics of fracture paths in heterogeneous rocks would be to use a DEM model with polyhedral elements to represent rock grains and intergranular space filled with cement or pores, which is not a focus of this study [55, 56].

Figs. 7a to e show the DEM results of the fluid injection rate effects, where different simulations are performed by means of stepwise addition of a certain fluid volume at the wellbore to achieve a constant flow rate loading. Initiation and propagation of a fracture, breakdown pressure at the first microcrack occurrence, and fluid flow along the newly formed fractures are micromechanically investigated in a two-dimensional biaxially compressed synthetic rock. The blue circles in Figs. 7a to e represent the fluid pressure in fluid flow reservoirs along the fracture.

Fig. 7a shows hydraulic fracturing at the very small or quasi-static strain rate 10^{-6} s^{-1} where the obtained breakdown pressure equals the value of Kirsch solution at $P_{b,Kirsch}=15.0 \text{ MPa}$, while Fig. 7b shows the results of hydraulic fracturing at the strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} , which is still considered quasi-static, with the breakdown pressure at $P_b=19.44 \text{ MPa}$. Comparing Figs. 7a and b, significant difference already exists at the micromechanical level. In Fig. 7a, fracture propagates as a bi-wing fracture, while in Fig. 7b fractures are shorter, and one fracture direction dominates the other. Pore pressures gradually decrease towards the fracture tip in Fig. 7a but are relatively high along the shorter fracture in Fig. 7b. It can be concluded that fluid flow in newly formed fracture is different for those two cases, which is a valuable conclusion. Fig. 7c shows results of hydraulic fracturing at a fast and nearly impact loading of 0.1 s^{-1} , with the breakdown pressure is 11.1% larger than in Fig. 7b. At a strain rate of about 0.1 s^{-1} , the breakdown pressure becomes strain rate dependent and deviates the from the Kirsch solution (Fig. 6) [54].

The micromechanical observation from the numerical model shows that the approximately 20 % breakdown pressure increase with higher loading rates from the ideal quasi-static case indicates significant deviation from the validity of Kirsch solution for obtaining the breakdown pressure and maximum allowable tensile stress at the wellbore wall using a very low viscosity fracturing fluid. High hydraulic fracturing strain rate results are

shown in Fig. 7d for 1 s^{-1} and in Fig. 7e for 10 s^{-1} . Fig. 7d shows breakdown pressure of $P_b=24.0$ MPa which is 23.5 % higher than in the Fig. 7a. Fig. 7e shows development of microcracks shown as blue lines in the figure around the wellbore, which do not follow the LEFM principles and are directionally independent from the far-field in situ stresses direction. Hydraulic fracturing strain rate increase causes significant branching and inhibits fluid inflow deeper to the fracture. Accompanied by fracture branching and microcracks, the high breakdown pressure is $P_b=34.8$ MPa, which is 97.5 % higher in Fig. 7e than in the Fig. 7b, and more than double from the value of Kirsch solution at $P_{b,Kirsch}=15$ MPa ($\sigma_{\min} = 7.0$ MPa, $\sigma_{\max} = 10.0$ MPa). Investigation of hydraulic fracturing flow rate effects shows micromechanical fracture damage after breakdown, resulting in very irregular spatial distribution of fluid pressures. Although the fracture branching is somewhat affected by the DEM discretization, the absence of it for a quasi-static case clearly shows that the rate effect is prominent, where fracturing still propagates perpendicular to the minimum in-situ far field compressive stress of the sample. For high flow rate the number of cracks is not increasing in a consistent way over time, while in quasi-static loading the number of cracks is increasing linearly with time.

3.4. Effect of Fracturing Fluid Viscosity and Matrix Permeability on Hydraulic Fracturing

3.4.1. Fluid Viscosity Effects

The effects of fracturing fluid dynamic viscosity on the hydraulic fracture initiation and propagation from the wellbore in quasi-brittle rock are investigated from the perspective of coupled H-M response. Field hydraulic fracturing trends towards varying the fluid viscosity during the fracturing treatment, starting with very low and gradually increasing. When higher fluid viscosities are used, the fracture width increases as predicted in linear elastic isotropic models [4]. Higher fluid viscosities are also used to transport proppant into the fracture. Simplified Newtonian fluids are used in this study for isolating effect of fluid dynamic viscosity from the shear rate dependency.

Fig. 8 shows fracture initiation from the wellbore for quasi-static pressurizing with different Newtonian fluids. Black arrows in Fig. 8 are DEM particle velocity vectors which indicate direction of particle motion and, therefore, the rock matrix deformation. The borehole area can be recognized as white disk in the middle of the model, with the fluid pressure indicated as blue disk. The borehole is pressurized with a constant pressure $P_b = 16.0$ MPa over longer time at $\Delta t=10^{-7}$ s. The ideal borehole breakdown pressure after Kirsch's solution in this

biaxially compressed model is $P_{b,id}=15.0$ MPa. In the case of highest fluid viscosity in Fig. 8a, there is no fluid flow in the fracture and fracture does not propagate. After the breakdown in the direction perpendicular to the minimum confinement far-field stress, the sample with lower fluid viscosity in Fig. 8c shows fluid infiltration into the fracture represented with blue disks. Fluid transfers pressure from the wellbore deeper into the newly formed fracture and enables fracture propagation. As a result, new microcracks appear in front of the existing fracture forming an un-wetted zone.

The observed scenarios yield qualitative understanding of the dependency of fracture initiation and propagation on fracturing fluid viscosity relative to time. Larger times are needed for hydraulic fracture to start propagating from the wellbore in case of higher fluid viscosities, which is micromechanically observed in the model. Larger pressure difference is needed to cause the flow of fluid in a channel as the fluid viscosity increases, as shown in Eq. (1), confirming the validity of the Eq. (1) for fluid flow in a fracture segment. Therefore, it can be concluded that higher fluid viscosities, in general, require increased pressure difference to induce the flow into a newly forming fracture, and, therefore, also further fracture micromechanical advancement and propagation. Fig. 8c shows a bi-wing fracture propagating from the wellbore using lower fluid viscosities and is a favorable scenario in hydraulic fracturing.

For investigating damage, and micro-cracks and fracture evolution a controlled stepped borehole pressure increase loading is used (Fig. 9). The non-porous rock model was chosen to isolate the effect of fluid viscosity at the wellbore and flowing into newly formed fractures, and to remove the poroelastic effects, as well as, the infiltration of the wellbore fluid into pores around the wellbore. The model with higher fluid viscosity of $\mu=100$ Pa·s was pressurized up to 26.0 MPa, while the wellbore pressure in the model with lower fluid viscosity of $\mu=10^{-5}$ Pa·s was stopped at 25.0 MPa. Fig. 10a shows the result of the model with lower fluid viscosity of $\mu=10^{-5}$ Pa·s, and Fig. 10b shows the result of the model with lower fluid viscosity of $\mu=100$ Pa·s. Low viscosity fluid result shown in Fig. 10a produced two-wing fractures which propagate from the borehole in the direction perpendicular to the minimum confinement stress ($\sigma_{max,v}=10.0$ MPa, $\sigma_{min,h}=6.0$ MPa). Cyan dots represent fluid pressure and infiltration in the fracture, blue lines are tensile microcracks and red lines are shear microcracks between particles. An un-wetted zone can be seen at the fracture tip in Fig. 10a. Unlike the case of low viscosity fluid, when high viscosity fluid is used in Fig. 10b, many fractures branch simultaneously form around the borehole in all directions. Very little fluid was able to infiltrate

the fractures as no cyan dots are present, and instead of fracture propagation, new fractures are formed around the borehole not following the LEFM preferred direction. This result suggests that caution is necessary when using higher fluid viscosity and especially in combination of increased pressurizing in hope of starting the fracture to propagate.

Results of a constant quasi-static flow rate fracturing are shown in Fig. 11, with a focus to better understand the borehole pressure drop and fluid flow in fracture. Three different fluid viscosities of $\mu_1=0.072$ Pa·s, $\mu_2=10^{-3}$ Pa·s and $\mu_3=10^{-7}$ Pa·s are used. Fig. 11 shows fracture and micro cracks around the wellbore a little bit after the anticipated breakdown, at $P_b=26$ MPa. The borehole pressure evolution is shown in Fig. 12 and it was around $P_b=24$ MPa for lower fluid viscosity samples in Figs. 11b and 11c, while the breakdown pressure does not occur for Fig. 11a with high viscosity fluid. As the fracturing fluid viscosity increases, two major observations can be made. First, the number of micro-cracks with damage character increases with fluid viscosity increase as shown in Fig. 11a where there is only damage around the wellbore, without a distinct fracture propagating. However, in Fig. 11c, a distinct bi-wing fracture propagates from the wellbore and it is filled with fluid represented by cyan circles. Second, the high viscosity fluid was not able to propagate the fracture from the wellbore, and as a result due to a constant inflow of the fluid into a wellbore during the time-stepping procedure, the wellbore pressure is constantly increasing.

The absence of the wellbore pressure-drop associated with the breakdown pressure in Fig. 12 is due to the absence of fracturing fluid flow in the new fracture segments. So, although the fracture initializes from the wellbore, the fluid is not able to subsequently flow into it, the wellbore pressure ramps up, and new microcracks simultaneously initiate at the wellbore wall forming damage. Combining the micromechanical insights in Fig. 11 and wellbore pressure monitoring in Fig 12, it can be concluded that changing fluid viscosity has no repercussions on the breakdown pressure, however, the fluid flow in the fracture cannot be established when high viscosity fluid is used resulting in extensive damage around wellbore. This conclusion cannot possibly be drawn by only observing the wellbore pressure.

3.4.2. Matrix Permeability Effects

Finally, rock matrix permeability is introduced in modeling dry rock. Simulations were performed with initial permeability zero (i.e., fluid channels between adjacent particles are initially closed until the parallel bond breaks), $k=8 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m² and $k=8 \cdot 10^{-14}$ m². However, due to pressurization and the stresses between particles, the size of flow channels may change, and the permeability locally decreases proportionally with the inter-particle contact force increase

and vice versa. The borehole boundary conditions are set as a constant fluid flow rate, and the borehole pressure was monitored during simulations.

Fig. 13a shows the comparison of fracture initiation pressure with low fluid dynamic viscosity ($\mu=10^{-7}$ Pa·s) for the impermeable, and low and high permeability synthetic granite sample. The initial pressures are 12 and 18 MPa, because starting from zero pressure would require significant computational time. The synthetic rock permeability does not significantly affect borehole pressure evolution when the low viscosity fluid is used, because the curves nearly match each other. The results show that the fracture initiation pressure is not significantly affected by rock matrix permeability. Fracturing continues at the same flow rate ($q=8.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$ m³/s) until the fracture almost reaches the sample boundary. The fracture propagation pressure is established at approximately 18 MPa. Fig. 13b shows a number of tensile micro cracks as broken normal bonds between particles versus the borehole pressure. The fracture propagation velocity can be estimated from Figs. 13a and b by observing the steady fracture propagation, time and number of cracks as $v=86$ cm/s in the case of aligned fractures.

In Fig. 14, the model fracture is shown for two cases of rock matrix permeability using low viscosity fluid. The results match with Fig. 10a where $\mu=10^{-5}$ Pa·s is used in impermeable rock sample. It can be concluded that for very low fluid viscosity, the models did not indicate a significant dependence of fracture breakdown pressure or fracture propagation on initial rock matrix permeability. This conclusion is constrained only to tight rock studied here, while for rocks with higher porosities and permeabilities such as is sandstone, the rock behavior may be different. However, as the fluid dynamic viscosity increases to water with $\mu=10^{-3}$ Pa·s, the rock permeability starts to play a role in hydro-mechanical rock response to hydraulic fracturing. Fig. 15a shows the borehole pressure evolution versus time for water fracturing in three permeability models, and Fig. 15b shows the respective wellbore pressure increase versus the number of microcracks. While impermeable sample still yielded a fracture like an LEFM prediction, the permeable samples show significantly different behavior with both respect of the breakdown pressure and microcracks. Fig. 15a shows wellbore pressure where the impermeable sample has breakdown pressure of approximately $P_b=24$ MPa while the permeable samples exhibit breakdown at $P_b=44$ MPa. Damage occurs around the wellbore instead of a single fracture propagating as can be seen in Figs. 16b and 16c, while the Fig. 16a shows a single propagating fracture.

Fig. 17 shows results of hydraulic fracture modeling using fluid dynamic viscosity of motor oil, $\mu=0.072$ Pa·s. The absence of fracture propagation is evident in Figs. 18a and b for both permeable and impermeable model. The damage zone consists of numerous microcracks which indicate lot of small fractures with short branches at the damage zone edges, without visible fluid infiltration.

4. Conclusions

A comprehensive micromechanical DEM study of the hydro-mechanical behavior of brittle dry crystalline rock was performed to improve understanding of the conditions that lead to fracture propagation and damage around wellbores during hydraulic fracturing. The following are the main conclusions from the study:

1. DEM models of permeable dry synthetic quasi-brittle rock, validated against laboratory rock mechanical data, has the capability to simulate rock hydraulic fracturing behavior across a wide range of flow rates with a single constant set of model parameters. This is a significant advantage of DEM modeling compared to other methods which employ different constitutive models for different flow rates. The predicted flow-rate dependent fracturing response from DEM modeling is attributed to its dynamic formulation and the use of damping to achieve quasi-static response. In DEM, the stress propagates following the p -wave equation and higher flow rates lead to higher stress concentration at the crack tip before enough bonds are broken to cause fracture propagation. As a result, fracture resistance increases with increasing flow rate. Also, hydraulic fracturing propagation rate increases as higher flow rates are used for pressure buildup in the wellbore. Micro-mechanical observations support this conclusion.
2. Micromechanical insights show that rock exhibits distinct hydraulic fracture propagation only at quasi-static flow rates of up to approximately 10^{-3} s⁻¹. As the flow rate increases above 10^{-3} s⁻¹, the rock around the wellbore becomes damaged with more diffused fracturing. The increase of damage occurs via a disconnected network of microcracks and short branched fractures, with an absence of clear LEFM-type preferential fracture propagation direction. Increase in wellbore pressure after breakdown is increasingly present as the flow rate increases further.
3. Fracturing fluid viscosity plays a significant effect on fracturing and damage around the wellbore. Pressure buildup at a constant flow rate during hydraulic fracturing occurs because of low mobility of high viscosity fluid into microcracks that form around the wellbore.

Lower fluid viscosities can flow and penetrate newly formed fracture segment relatively fast, so that the wellbore pressure release becomes evident as the breakdown pressure is reached. However, if the fluid flow rate into the wellbore is high and the inflow into fracture is low, the pressure build-up at the wellbore causes multiple fracturing in all directions around the wellbore wall.

4. Damage zones, which are formed around the wellbore, occur due to the same micromechanical mechanism around the wellbore for high flow rates with low viscosity fluids and quasi-static flow rates with high viscosity fluid. This phenomenon can be explained by offset of intense damage around the wellbore caused by inability of the fluid to move down the newly formed fracture segment and resulting fast pressure buildup in the wellbore.
5. Initial rock matrix permeability helps in fluid migration through the porous matrix and affects damage around the newly formed fractures. Numerical simulations revealed low viscosity fluid fracturing to be favorable and not affected by rock permeability, while when high viscosity fluids were used, extensive damage zone was observed in both laboratory experiments and numerical model.

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Table 1. Model initial and boundary conditions for hydraulic fracturing study, $\sigma_{min,y}$ = minimum compressive stress, $\sigma_{max,y}$ = maximum compressive stress, k_n is the wall normal stiffness, k_s is the wall shear stiffness, and μ is the wall friction coefficient.

Parameter	Magnitude
$\sigma_{min,z}$	6.0 - 25.0 MPa
$\sigma_{max,y}$	10.0 – 35.0 MPa
k_n	200 GPa
k_s	77 GPa
μ	0.0

Table 2. Macro-mechanical properties of BPM compared to the average granite from various sources (Engineering Toolbox).

Model	Tensile Strength, σ_t (MPa)	Young's Modulus, E (GPa)	Fracture Toughness, K_{IC} (MPa \sqrt{m})	Poisson's Ratio, ν (-)
PFC2D	4.37	57.7	0.31	0.21
Granite	3-25	30.0 - 70.0	0.22 - 1.55	0.25

Table 3. Micro-mechanical properties of the DEM-BPM model, R_{min} = minimum particle radius; R_{max} = maximum particle radius; f_i = particle friction coefficient; P_{b_kn} = parallel bond normal stiffness; P_{b_ks} = parallel bond shear stiffness; P_{b_sstr} = parallel bond shear strength; P_{b_nstr} = parallel bond normal strength; and w_0 = initial fluid channel aperture.

Parameter	Value
R_{min} (m)	0.0011
R_{max}/R_{min} (-)	1.66
f_i (-)	0.2
P_{b_kn} (GPa)	7.0
P_{b_ks} (GPa)	2.8
P_{b_sstr} (MPa)	30.0
P_{b_nstr} (MPa)	10.0
w_0 (m)	$10^{-5}/10^{-7}$

Table 4. Results for the strain-rate dependent fracture initiation stress σ_f in synthetic granite.

Strain Rate	Fracture Initiation Stress: DEM	Fracture Initiation Stress: Theoretical
$d\varepsilon_0/dt$ (s^{-1})	σ_f (MPa)	σ_f (MPa)
100	72	66.5
10	34.8 – 58.0	31.0
1	24.0-26.4	14.2 (expression not valid)
0.1	21.6	(expression not valid)
0.001	18.4	15

Figure 1. Details of the micromechanical model, yellow disks are DEM particles and blue disks are fluid reservoirs, connected with fluid channels.

Figure 2a. Model setup for numerical testing of synthetic rock sample permeability, with constant fluid reservoir pressures on the left boundary, represented with green disks and DEM particles represented with red disks.

Figure 2b. Pressure profile evolution with time across the model with for permeability measurement.

Figure 3. Calibration of the average model permeability, a) average model permeability vs. initial fluid channel aperture with target values for the synthetic rock sample, and b) permeability vs. initial pressure curve for the synthetic rock.

Figure 4. Laboratory experimental setup (left), and specimen fractured with water, example cross-section taken from the confined granite specimen after hydraulic fracturing with a detail view highlighting a dyed individual fracture (right) [53, 54].

Figure 5. Qualitative comparison of the fractured laboratory [53, 54] and DEM biaxially confined samples, where DEM model has initial permeability $k=8 \cdot 10^{-14}$, obtained using motor oil with $\mu=0.072$ Pa·s at quasi-static pressurization

Figure 6. Validation of the DEM bonded model: mechanical behavior of synthetic rock subjected to hydraulic fracturing across loading rates from quasi-static to dynamic.

Figure 7. Micromechanical response of synthetic rock showing fluid pressures in fluid flow reservoirs (blue disks) for different loading rates from quasi-static to impact loading.

Figure 8. Fluid viscosity effect on impermeable rock fracturing under constant $P_b=16,0 \text{ MPa}$ wellbore pressures. (Kirsch solution breakdown pressure is $P_{b,id}=15 \text{ MPa}$)

Figure 9. Staged increase in borehole pressure versus time.

Figure 10. Micromechanics of hydraulic fracturing of synthetic impermeable rock when subjected to the stage pressurizing at the borehole with a) low dynamic viscosity $\mu=10^{-5}$ Pa·s and b) high dynamic viscosity $\mu=100$ Pa·s.

Figure 11. Microcracks developed under the staged borehole pressurizing in impermeable rock, subjected to identical borehole pressure using low, medium and high viscosity fluids (legend the same as in Fig. 8).

Figure 12. The borehole pressure evolution versus time during quasi-static hydraulic fracturing with three fluids of different dynamic viscosities in impermeable synthetic rock.

Figure 13. The borehole pressure evolution versus (a) time and (b) number of microcracks during hydraulic fracturing with low viscosity fluid $\mu=10^{-7}$ Pa·s.

Figure 14. Bi-wing hydraulic fracture for low viscosity fracturing fluid in permeable synthetic rock ($\mu=10^{-7}$ Pa·s) (legend the same as in Fig. 8).

Figure 15. The borehole pressure evolution versus (a) time and (b) number of microcracks for water ($\mu=10^{-3}$ Pa·s) in impermeable and two permeable synthetic rock models.

Figure 16. Micromechanics of hydraulic fracture propagation with water ($\mu=10^{-3}$ Pa·s) as fracturing fluid in a) impermeable and permeable b) $k=8 \cdot 10^{-14}$ m² and c) $k=8 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m² (legend the same as in Fig. 8).

Figure 17. The borehole pressure evolution versus (a) time and (b) number of microcracks for hydraulic fracturing of impermeable and permeable synthetic rock using high viscosity fluid ($\mu=0.072 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) (legend the same as in Fig. 8).

Figure 18. Micromechanics of hydraulic fracture propagation using high viscosity fluid ($\mu=0.072 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) in impermeable and permeable synthetic rock (legend the same as in Fig. 8).